

**ENGLISH TRANSLATION OF ALEXANDER FEINBERG'S POEM
ABOUT HIS MOTHER**

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Spring finished- I didn't come to the cemetery,

Suddenly I saw on the doorstep.

It wasn't snow that falling from the sky,

It was my mother's dear scarf.

I wonder whether I saw it or not?

November—in my yard, I could sense it.

Birthday. It was her birthday

November is my mother's birthday

In Uzbek:

Ko'klam o'tdi—qabristonga kelmadim,

ILM – FAN TA'LIMDA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR, MUAMMOLAR, TAKLIF VA
YECHIMLAR

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Bo'sag'ada ko'zim tushdi nogohon.
Ko'kdan tushayotgan qormas, bilmadim,
Onamning ro'moli edi shodumon.
Yoxud ko'zlarimga ko'rindimi u?
Hovlimda—noyabr. Sezdim bu damni—
Tug'ilgan kun. Tug'ilgan kun edi bu —
Noyabr —tavallud oyi onamning